

Variance Reduction for Dynamic Monte Carlo Using Forced Correlation Derived from Stochastic Calculus

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DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20803146

ABSTRACT

This paper introduces a new variance–reduction algorithm for the Dynamic Monte Carlo (DMC) method, referred to as forced correlation. The approach exploits correlations between adjacent time steps and is derived using the Non-Analog Monte Carlo (NAMC) noise model, which represents DMC calculations through stochastic differential equations (SDEs). The formulation of forced correlation is presented in both its SDE form and its corresponding Monte Carlo implementation. Numerical results demonstrate the reduction in variance achieved when applying the forced correlation algorithm.

Keywords: Dynamic Monte Carlo method, forced correlation, stochastic calculus, stochastic point-kinetics, non-analog Monte Carlo model

1. INTRODUCTION

Upon the increasing computational capacities, Monte Carlo (MC) has reached a state in nuclear techniques where it can be seen as an ultimate tool to determine the neutron transport of reactors. In [1], the MC method for steady-state calculations was summarized decades ago, shifting the research focus of MC toward the direction of Dynamic Monte Carlo (DMC). The steady-state and time-dependent simulations do not differ from the MC perspective on the surface due to the implicit time passing during neutron transport; however, using the same operator formalism in both cases waited until [2], which extended it to DMC. Indeed, the DMC method allows the simulation of neutrons and the environment in time, which appears as a stochastic process instead of a single state under stochastic uncertainty. This stochastic process is constructed as follows: the time of the simulations is divided into finite time bins where the tallied neutron population gives the value of the process at each time bin. In other words, the stochastic process of the DMC method can be interpreted as the series of tallies over time, although the operator formalism of [2] does not determine the sought stochastic process in detail. The difference between the operator formalism and the stochastic-process representation stands in the MC integration, since the operator formalism relates to the expectation of the neutron transport, which becomes stochastic only after performing MC integrations. Therefore, altering the simulation of neutrons in a non-analog way and using variance reduction methods are beneficial for DMC calculations, as they can decelerate the increase of uncertainty in the neutron transport as a stochastic process. Such variance reduction methods have been investigated before, like the forced decay in [3] or the forced fission in [4], to name a few. Still, finding new variance reduction methods remains a key research topic for MC calculations in the present and the future to make the simulations more and more effective.

The operator formalism of the DMC method is not the only possible way to express the nature of the DMC simulations. In [5], the Non-Analog Monte Carlo (NAMC) noise model was introduced to model

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the DMC method with stochastic differential equations (SDEs). It required the modification of the original Stochastic Point-Kinetics (SPK) equation [6] that represented the analog noise of neutrons. This NAMC noise model proved successful in handling and describing the variance reduction of forced fission in [7], which opened the possibility to find more variance reduction algorithms with the help of the NAMC noise model.

The paper is structured as follows: Sec. 2 establishes the ground of the research by introducing the basics of SDEs and the NAMC noise model. Next, Sec. 3 explains and unfolds all the new results, namely the algorithm of forced correlation and its numerical illustration. Finally, Sec. 4 concludes the results of this paper.

2. THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

2.1. Stochastic Differential Equations

Stochastic ordinary differential equations (SODEs) [8] provide a mathematical framework for describing stochastic processes in time by combining deterministic evolution with random fluctuations. Using SODEs, external or internal noise can be incorporated into an otherwise deterministic system, extending the original behavior. The stochastic processes modeled by SODEs are continuous in both time and state, allowing the state to evolve over an uncountably infinite set of possible values. Let us define a deterministic process $x(t)$ in general form as:

$$\frac{dx(t)}{dt} = \mu(t, x(t)) , \quad (1)$$

where $\mu(t, x(t))$ is the drift function of the process. Transforming Eq. 1 into a SODE yields to the stochastic process $X(t)$ written as:

$$dX(t) = \mu(t, X(t)) dt + \sigma(t, X(t)) dW(t) , \quad (2)$$

where $\sigma(t, X(t))$ is the diffusion function and $W(t)$ is a Wiener process. The SODE in Eq. 2 is driven by Gaussian white noise through the increment $dW(t)$, which is a standard modeling approach for continuous-time stochastic systems. The system coefficients $\mu(t, X(t))$ and $\sigma(t, X(t))$ are deterministic functions that characterize the deterministic and stochastic components of the process. For physical modeling, these coefficients must be derived or inferred from the underlying system behavior.

From a mathematical perspective, the drift and diffusion functions can be expressed in terms of the transition probability $\mathbf{P}(t)$ and the transition increment $\Delta X(t)$ of the stochastic process $X(t)$ over a sufficiently small time interval Δt . Given $\mathbf{P}(t)$ and $\Delta X(t)$, the drift function is obtained as:

$$\mu(t, X(t)) = \lim_{\Delta t \rightarrow 0} \frac{\mathbf{P}(t)}{\Delta t} \cdot \Delta X(t) , \quad (3)$$

and the diffusion function as:

$$\sigma(t, X(t)) = \lim_{\Delta t \rightarrow 0} \sqrt{\frac{\mathbf{P}(t)}{\Delta t}} \cdot \Delta X(t) . \quad (4)$$

Eq. 3 and Eq. 4 illustrate that the SODE in Eq. 2 originates from the elemental transitions that may occur during the evolution of the stochastic process. In what follows, we make use of these elemental reactions in our modeling framework.

2.2. Non-Analog Monte Carlo Noise Model of the Stochastic Point-Kinetics equation

The NAMC noise model [5] is a possible noise representation of the SPK equation [6] and corresponds to the non-analog transport description of neutron behavior. It enables the description of noise characteristics that differ from the analog case and leads to an alternative representation of the DMC method,

see [5]. Within the SPK framework, the NAMC noise model tracks the number of neutrons $N(t)$, which is written as:

$$N(t) = N_s(t) \cdot w_N(t), \quad (5)$$

where $N_s(t)$ denotes the number of simulated neutrons and $w_N(t)$ is their statistical weight. In the case of a branchless algorithm and perfect weight control, N_s remains constant and all simulated neutrons share the same weight $w_N(t)$.

We consider the external-sourceless SPK equation without delayed neutrons and introduce the parameters ρ as the reactivity, Λ as the neutron generation time, v as the average neutron velocity and ν as the average neutron yield from one fission. The relevant interactions are characterized by the macroscopic capture (Σ^c), fission (Σ^f) and scattering (Σ^s) cross sections, which determine the transition probabilities and transition rates of the underlying stochastic process. In this modeling we apply implicit capture, a variance reduction technique leading to non-analog scattering that incorporates capture events. Without employing forced fission, the fission transition is written as [5] [7]:

$$\mathbf{P}_F = N^s \Sigma^f v \Delta t \quad (6a)$$

$$[\Delta N]_F = \mathbf{R}_F \cdot [w^N] = [-1 + \nu] \cdot [w^N], \quad (6b)$$

where \mathbf{P}_F is the transition probability of fission and $[\Delta N]_F$ is the transition rate of fission. The scattering transition is defined analogously [5] [7]:

$$\mathbf{P}_S = N^s (\Sigma^c + \Sigma^s) v \Delta t \quad (7a)$$

$$[\Delta N]_S = \mathbf{R}_S \cdot [w^N] = \left[-1 + \frac{\Sigma^s}{(\Sigma^c + \Sigma^s)} \right] \cdot [w^N], \quad (7b)$$

where \mathbf{P}_S is the transition probability of scattering and $[\Delta N]_S$ is the transition rate of scattering. Eq. 6 and Eq. 7 together yield the prompt SPK equation driven by the NAMC noise model:

$$dN = \frac{\rho}{\Lambda} N dt + \sqrt{\frac{-\rho + (v - 1 - V_{ic})}{\Lambda N^s}} N dW, \quad (8)$$

where V_{ic} is the variance reduction parameter associated with implicit capture. Variance reduction aims to diminish the stochastic term in Eq. 8, since a smaller diffusion coefficient results in a slower growth of statistical variance over time.

3. RESULTS

3.1. Derivation of the Forced Correlation Algorithm

The non-analog diffusion function can take as many forms as the different reaction sets that produce the same expectation. If our objective is variance reduction, we must adjust $(\mathbf{P}_F, [\Delta N]_F)$ and $(\mathbf{P}_S, [\Delta N]_S)$ until the resulting variance decreases. A similar optimization was performed for the optimal forced-fission coefficient in [7]. Here we introduce a new reaction, referred to as correlation, arising from the forced correlation algorithm. This reaction is characterized by the following transition probability and transition rate:

$$\mathbf{P}_c^{fc} = 1 \quad (9a)$$

$$[\Delta N]_c^{fc} = \left[\mathbf{P}_F^{fc} \mathbf{R}_F^{fc} + \mathbf{P}_S^{fc} \mathbf{R}_S^{fc} \right] \cdot [w_c^N], \quad (9b)$$

where $w_c^N(t)$ is an appropriately chosen weight. We now redefine Eq. 6 and Eq. 7 under the condition that their drift functions, obtained from Eq. 3, remain unchanged. Under this constraint, the fission

transition becomes:

$$\mathbf{P}_F^{fc} = N^s \Sigma^f v \Delta t \quad (10a)$$

$$[\Delta N]_F^{fc} = \mathbf{R}_F^{fc} \cdot [w^N - w_c^N] = [-1 + \nu] \cdot [w^N - w_c^N] . \quad (10b)$$

Similarly, the scattering transition is rewritten as:

$$\mathbf{P}_S^{fc} = N^s (\Sigma^c + \Sigma^s) v \Delta t \quad (11a)$$

$$[\Delta N]_S^{fc} = \mathbf{R}_S^{fc} \cdot [w^N - w_c^N] = \left[-1 + \frac{\Sigma^s}{(\Sigma^c + \Sigma^s)} \right] \cdot [w^N - w_c^N] . \quad (11b)$$

We assume that the DMC calculation employs sufficiently small time steps such that no significant change occurs in the neutron population during a single step. This assumption permits the identification $w_c^N(t)$ as $w_c^N(t) = w^N(t - \Delta t)$, meaning that the correlated weight is essentially the weight at the previous time step. Thus, the previous state of the neutron population becomes the initial condition for the next step, with only small corrections introduced by fission and scattering. Using Eq. 9, Eq. 10 and Eq. 11, we obtain the following SODE for the prompt SPK equation:

$$dN = \frac{\rho}{\Lambda} N dt + \sqrt{\frac{-\rho + (\nu - 1 - V_{ic})}{\Lambda N^s}} (N - N_c) dW_1 + \sqrt{\frac{|\rho|}{\Lambda N^s}} N_c dW_2 , \quad (12)$$

where $N_c(t) = N(t - \Delta t)$. The presence of two stochastic terms in Eq. 12 yields a smaller total variance than the single stochastic term in Eq. 8. This demonstrates that modifying the reaction set successfully reduces the variance predicted by the NAMC noise model. The theoretical derivation therefore indicates that the forced correlation algorithm can provide significant benefits for DMC calculations.

3.2. Numerical Illustration of the Forced Correlation Algorithm

Forced correlation can be incorporated into the weight equations of the simplified DMC scheme, allowing us to illustrate its effect on the variance. Here, we take the same simplified DMC algorithm as in [7] and modify its weight equations as follows:

$$w_{n,i}^{r+1} \stackrel{f}{=} \left(\left[\mathbf{P}_F^{fc} - 1 \right] \mathbf{R}_F^{fc} + \mathbf{P}_S^{fc} \mathbf{R}_S^{fc} \right) \bar{w}_i + \left(\mathbf{R}_F^{fc} - 1 \right) w_{n,i}^r , \quad (13a)$$

$$w_{n,i}^{r+1} \stackrel{s}{=} \left(\mathbf{P}_F^{fc} \mathbf{R}_F^{fc} + \left[\mathbf{P}_S^{fc} - 1 \right] \mathbf{R}_S^{fc} \right) \bar{w}_i + \left(\mathbf{R}_S^{fc} - 1 \right) w_{n,i}^r . \quad (13b)$$

Eq. 13 describe how the simplified DMC algorithm updates the weight of the n -th simulated neutron after the r -th reaction on the time interval $[t_i, t_{i+1}]$. Here, \bar{w}_i denotes the average weight of the simulated neutrons over the same time interval.

As a demonstration case, we consider a reactor configuration defined in Table I, which includes subcritical, critical, and supercritical conditions. For this problem, neutron kinetics is solved using four approaches: (1) the original version of the simplified DMC algorithm; (2) the forced correlation version of the simplified DMC algorithm, as defined by Eq. 13; (3) the original SPK with the NAMC noise model, given by Eq. 8; and (4) the forced correlation version of the SPK with the NAMC noise model, given by Eq. 12. In the simplified DMC calculations, neutron chains are tracked in time steps of $5 \cdot 10^{-6}$ s, with reactions sampled using random numbers. In contrast, the SPK equations are solved using the Implicit Euler–Maruyama method [9], also with a time step of $5 \cdot 10^{-6}$ s. In terms of computational cost, a single realization of the original and the forced correlation DMC algorithms required 93.9 s and 99.8 s, respectively.

Fig. 1, Fig. 2 and Fig. 3 present the relative standard deviations of the reactor power obtained with and without forced correlation, for both the simplified DMC and SPK approaches. It can be observed that the

Figure 1. Relative standard deviations of the power in the subcritical state with 10^5 simulated neutrons. The figure contains the results of the simplified DMC algorithm without (blue) and with (red) applying forced correlation and the solution of the Non-Analog Monte Carlo (NAMC) noise model (black). The statistics were made by 250 realizations.

Figure 2. Relative standard deviations of the power in the critical state with 10^5 simulated neutrons. The figure contains the results of the simplified DMC algorithm without (blue) and with (red) applying forced correlation and the solution of the Non-Analog Monte Carlo (NAMC) noise model (black). The statistics were made by 250 realizations.

Table I. Parameters of the kinetical calculations in subcritical, critical and supercritical cases.

-	ρ [pcm]	v [cm/s]	ν [-]	Σ^c [1/cm]	Σ^f [1/cm]	Σ^s [1/cm]
Subcritical	-7692.31	$2.0 \cdot 10^5$	2.5	0.4400	0.2600	0.30
Critical	0.0	$2.0 \cdot 10^5$	2.5	0.4200	0.2800	0.30
Supercritical	+284.9	$2.0 \cdot 10^5$	2.5	0.4192	0.2808	0.30

Figure 3. Relative standard deviations of the power in the supercritical state with 10^5 simulated neutrons. The figure contains the results of the simplified DMC algorithm without (blue) and with (red) applying forced correlation and the solution of the Non-Analog Monte Carlo (NAMC) noise model (black). The statistics were made by 250 realizations.

variance decreases over time for all reactor states when forced correlation is applied, demonstrating the effectiveness of the forced correlation algorithm. As expected, the NAMC noise model results exhibit smaller relative standard deviations, consistent with the idealized assumption of perfect weight control. Figure 1 further indicates that, for a strongly non-critical prompt-neutron chain, applying the forced-correlation algorithm may lead to a higher relative standard deviation in the SPK calculations. However, this trend is not observed in the simplified DMC results.

4. CONCLUSIONS

This paper presented a new application of the NAMC noise model to the DMC method by investigating a variance reduction technique referred to as forced correlation. The transition probabilities and transition rates of the non-analog reactions under forced correlation were derived for the prompt SPK equation, emphasizing the modification of the stochastic term relative to the original formulation. In addition, the forced correlation algorithm was evaluated using a simplified DMC calculation, demonstrating a consistent reduction in variance. Since variance reduction through forced correlation relies primarily on previously generated simulation data, this technique can, in principle, be extended to space- and energy-dependent problems, including cases with delayed neutrons.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This paper was supported by the Ministry of Innovation and Technology of Hungary from the National Research, Development and Innovation Fund, financed under Grants VKSZ 14-1-2015-0021, TKP2021-NVA-02 and ADVANCED 152888.

This research was sponsored by the HUN-REN Office for Supported Research Groups (TKI) under the Award No. TKCS-2024/56.

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